

RSETIs, Human Resource Management: A Unique Scheme for Self-Employment for Rural Youths of India

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Abstract

Unemployment is a serious issue in our country as lakhs of youths, both male, female, and even transgender, have been entering the job market every year, both from rural and urban areas. Still, employment needs to be generated as per the demand. The unemployment rate in India means the number of people actively looking for a job, calculated as a percentage of the labour force. Self-employment is one of the alternatives to address the issue of unemployment. Rural Self-Employment Training Institute, popularly known as RSETI, which the banks manage with active cooperation from the Government of India and the State Government for promoting self-employment, has been discussed here. For this, both secondary data and based on field study cases have been presented here. The cases have been presented from a) Samastipur District, Bihar b) Darrang District, Assam, c) Amritsar District, Punjab, d) Nizamabad District, Telangana, e) Guntur District, Andhra Pradesh f) Murshidabad District, West Bengal and g) West Khasi Hills District, Meghalaya.

Keywords: Income, RSETI, Self-employment, Unemployment and Youths.

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FULL PAPER

Introduction: About RSETIs

In any country, after completing education, an adult person requires earnings for his/her sustenance. In general, earnings can be of two types: either through working in others' organizations (wage-employment) or through self-employment. It is a fact that wage employment cannot be provided to all, so alternative is self-employment. It is pertinent to mention that according to the latest survey, the share of self-employed persons in the total employed population in India has increased from 52 percent in 2018-2019 to 57 percent in 2022-2023. Interestingly, the shares of both casual and regular wage earners in the total employed population have decreased.

Rural Self-Employment Training Institutes (RSETIs), an initiative of the Ministry of Rural Development (MoRD), have been functioning in India to provide self-employment to rural youths. As of November 2024, our country has 585 functional RSETIs across India, with at least one in each district. Since its inception, RSETIs have trained over 44 lakh candidates. A little over 70 percent of RSETI trainees have settled into self-employment. RSETIs offer 64 training programs approved by the National Council for Vocational Education and Training (NCVET) and the Ministry of Rural Development (MoRD). RSETI training programmes are short-term interventions that last one to six weeks. RSETIs offer hand-holding support, including bank financial assistance, to help trainees start their businesses. Trainees are also given space to showcase and sell their products at events like SARAS mela (nirdpr.org.in/rseti)

Figure 1: Training Provided at RSETIs

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RSETIs are managed by banks with active cooperation from the Government of India and the State Governments. RSETI concept is based on RUDSETI (Rural Development and Self Employment Training Institute), a society established jointly by three organisations, viz., Syndicate Bank, Canara Bank and Sri Manjunatheswara Trust located at Ujire in Karnataka. It is noteworthy to mention that Dr. D.Veerendra Heggade, Dharmadhikari (President) of Dharmasthala, Social Reformer, Educationist, Philosopher and Philanthropist, is the key person to establish RUDSETI (Rural Development and Self Employment Training Institute).

The lead bank is responsible for forming and managing RSETIs in each district. The Government of India provides a one-time grant of up to Rs. One crore to meet the expenditure on building and other infrastructure. The common minimum infrastructure of each RSETI is 2-3 classrooms with toilet facilities (separate for women and physically challenged friendly), and two workshops, two dormitories with bath facilities. In addition, adequate physical infrastructure for training, administration, hostel, staff quarters etc. are arranged.

Each RSETI offers 30 to 40 skill development programmes in a financial year in various trades. The Programmes are from one week to six weeks. Some programmes are Agricultural Programme, Product Programme, Process Programme etc. The Agricultural Programme includes agriculture and allied activities like dairy, poultry, apiculture, horticulture, sericulture, mushroom cultivation, floriculture, fisheries, etc. The other is the Product Programme – dress designs for men and women, incense sticks manufacturing, football making, bags, bakery products, leaf cup making, recycled paper manufacturing, etc. Another one is Process Programme – two-wheeler repairs, radio/TV repairs, motor rewinding, electrical transformer repairs, irrigation pump-set repairs, tractor and power tiller repairs, cell phone repairs, beautician course, photography and videography, screen printing, domestic electrical appliances repair, computer hardware, and DTP. Also, there are other programmes based on local needs. At least 70 percent of the trainees should be from rural below-poverty-line families (BPL category). Also, SC/STs, minorities, physically challenged, and women are accommodated in the training. In each batch, 25-30 youths are trained. After successfully completing training, youths are provided credit (if willing) to set up their businesses. This author studied nationwide and found that the concept of RSETIs is good as many youths could start their own venture.

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Trainees of RSETI:

RSETI (Rural Self Employment Training Institutes) programme is a three-way partnership between the Ministry of Rural Development (MoRD), the Government of India, State Governments, and the Sponsor Banks. The Banks must open at least one RSETI in their lead district to train rural youth to take up self-employment/ entrepreneurship ventures. RSETI programme runs with an approach of short-term training & long-term handholding of entrepreneurs. Rural poor youth between the age group of 18-45 years.

Figure 2: RSETI (Rural Self Employment Training Institutes)

Each RSETI generally offers 30 to 40 skill development programmes in various trades during the financial year.

- a) Agricultural Programmes – agriculture and allied activities like dairy, poultry, apiculture, horticulture, sericulture, mushroom cultivation, floriculture, fisheries, etc.
- b) Product Programme – dress designs for men and women, incense sticks manufacturing, football making, bag, bakery products, leaf cup making, recycled paper manufacturing, etc.
- c) Process Programmes – two-wheeler repairs, radio/TV repairs, motor rewinding, electrical transformer repairs, irrigation pump-set repairs, tractor, and power tiller repairs, cell phone repairs, beautician course, photography and videography, screen printing, domestic electrical appliances repair, computer hardware and DTP.
- d) General Programmes – skill development for women

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- e) Other Programmes – related to other sectors like leather, construction, hospitality, and any other sector depending on local requirements.

Field Situation:

From time to time, the author has conducted studies in different RSETIs across India. Some of the studies based on field situations are presented here.

I wish to start my presentation from the RSETI, Samastipur district of Bihar. RSETI. I visited the RSETI in July 2019.

A) Samastipur, Bihar: RSETI at Samastipur was set up in March 2011 under the umbrella of Union Bank. During the discussion, the Director of the RSETI informed that it was functioning in a rented building. However, land for the new building was allotted, but because of some legal hassle, work was delayed, and it would be started in October 2019. The Director further informed that since its inception and till the day of study, there was no provision for night staying and that training programmes were not residential because of rented buildings. In addition to the Director, one woman faculty and one attended worked, so the staff is also less.

From inception to June 2019, altogether, 150 courses were conducted where 4454 youths were trained in different trades like women's dresses, dairy, vermicompost, mobile repairing, beauty parlour, agarbatti making, mushroom cultivation, beekeeping, goat rearing, etc. Of the 4454 trained youths, female and male were 1986 and 2468 respectively. Again, of the 4454 youths, 3269 were settled with self-employment, and six got wage employment. Of the many names studied by the author as cases, four names that benefitted are mentioned here. All started their trades by borrowing through bank loans and own money, so details are not presented here.

1. Ashok Kumar (other backward castes, 26 years in July 2018), was from below the poverty line (BPL) and was benefitted by beekeeping training. He was earning on average a sum of Rs. 20,000.00 per month.
2. Arati Mishra (other caste, Postgraduate, 27 years in March 2017) underwent tailoring training and started her unit. Arati Mishra, after paying wage to one worker (whom

she employed) and repaying bank loan was earning an average Rs 15,000.00 per month.

3. Kiran Kumari (28 years old woman in May 2015, HSLC), after training in a beauty parlour started the unit by employing one woman worker. According to her, her net monthly earnings were Rs 22,000.00 when the study was conducted.

4. Sanjeev Kumar Singh (32 years old, male, in October 2017, OBC) was trained in poultry farm management. By employing one person and repaying bank loan, his average earning was Rs25,000.00 per month.

B) Darrang District, Assam: The study was conducted in February 2018. Two cases are presented here out of 24 trainees.

1. Ms. Poly Seal (32 years/HSLC Pass) and 23 women were trained in soft toy making. The training was conducted in November 2017 for 13 days. Her husband had a petty business, so she took an interest in RSETI's soft toy-making training to earn some income. When the author interviewed her in February 2018, she said she had applied for a loan to the Punjab National Bank (PNB) to the tune of Rs. 2 lakh, and if the same were sanctioned, she would expand her business. Because, till the day of study, she was making the toys at a small scale in her home, fetching an average monthly net income of Rs. 4,000.

2: Ms. Mousami Saikia Gogoi (35 years/HSSLC Pass) underwent training in a beauty parlour in May 2017. Her husband was in a job, and the son would be appearing in the HSLC examination, so she wanted to earn more. Even then, she was doing her activity from her home only, which fetched monthly earnings of Rs. 5,000.

C) Amritsar District, Punjab:

To get an idea about the trainees of RSETI in Amritsar district of Punjab, the study was conducted in the first week of August 2017. Altogether, 29 women completed their training on dress designing (tailoring), which started on July 4, 2017, and was completed on August 2, 2017. It was not a residential training as the building for the stay was not completed till the day of the study, but all the trainees were provided with free lunch and tea with snacks twice. The Centre/ Institute was started in March 2011 by a local Gurudawara and later shifted to its building in Mallian, where the Institute has been functioning permanently under the leadership of Punjab National Bank (PNB), as PNB is the lead bank in the district.

1. Jasbir Kaur (40 years, married), Higher Secondary School Leaving Certificate (HSSLC) passed and lived with three children – two more than 18 years old, and one was in sixth standard. Jasbir Kaur's husband had a shoe shop. During the road widening, shops were dismantled, and her husband was also victimized, so to support the family, she was stitching clothes at home as she had an idea about tailoring. When she learned about RSETI's training, she completed the same (dress designing), and after the RSETI's training, she applied to KVIC for Rs.1 lakh as a subsidy and Rs. 2 lakh as a loan.
2. Harjit Kaur (21 years, HSSLC pass) subsequently completed her Diploma in ITI. After completing RSETI's training, she applied for a loan of Rs.50,000 to start her own business. Her father was a daily labourer.

D) Nizamabad District, Telangana:

1. Ch. Ashok is a resident of Dichpally village, of Dichpally mandal, Nizamabad district of Telangana. He studied up to the Intermediate level, but after his father's death (small businessman), Ashok had to take responsibility for the family. He was interested in the Multi Phone Servicing trade and attended a training programme in November 2014 at RSETI of the State Bank of Hyderabad in Nizamabad. After training, he established a mobile shop with around Rs.1.50 lakh. According to him, the average monthly earning hovers around Rs. 13,000.
2. Ms. T. Latha studied up to the fifth standard (married) and was from a below-poverty-line (BPL) family before undergoing RSETI training. Her husband worked as a daily wage earner, which was inadequate to sustain the family. To earn the additional income, she decided to start a tailoring unit. She did not have sufficient prowess, so she approached SBH RSETI, Dichpally, Nizamabad district, and in 2014 (28/11/2014 to 29/12/2014), she was trained in the trade. Upon completion of training, she established a tailoring unit at her residence, and her earnings hovered around Rs. 7,000 per month, which was additional income for a family.

E) Guntur District, Andhra Pradesh :

1. Adapa Kalpana (34 years old woman, belongs to OC) hails from Dharanikota village of Amaravathi mandal, Guntur district of Andhra Pradesh. She is a housewife (studied up to tenth class), was also involved in tailoring to supplement income to the family, and was earning a meager monthly income of Rs.4,000 per month. Her husband was working in a finance company. To scale up her income, she decided to start fashion designing. Accordingly, she

joined RSETI, Guntur, sponsored by Andhra Bank in July 2013, and subsequently, in October 2014, she started her at Dharanikota village with an investment of Rs.2 lakh by availing bank loan of Rs. 40,000 from the State Bank of Hyderabad under MUDRA Scheme and the balance amount of Rs.1.60 Lakh was invested by her savings. In 2016, as reported, her net monthly income on average was Rs. 15,000. Further, she employed one person and trained six members in tailoring activities.

2. Ch. Veera Brahmaiah, aged 35 years (OBC), is a resident of Amaravathi town of Guntur District. He studied up to the tenth class and also completed ITI. His father was an agricultural labourer, and his earning was too meager to sustain a family. To support his father, Veera Brahmaiah underwent Electric Motor Rewinding training in February 2006, and after training, he started his venture at Amaravathi in April 2015 with a sum of Rs. 2 lakh – Rs. 30,000 as bank loan and the rest his investment. He could earn a net monthly income of Rs 40,000, as reported in April 2016, which changed his life to a great extent, and economic hardship scaled down substantially.

F) Murshidabad District, West Bengal:

Fulchand Shaikh is from Pratappur village in Murshidabad District of West Bengal. He could not continue his studies after the tenth standard because of family problems. On the other hand, he had been looking for a suitable job for several years but was unsuccessful. One day, he came to know about RUDSETI (initially, it was RUDSETI, as mentioned already). He was trained in mobile repairing at RUDSETI, Berhampore, West Bengal. After the training, he received a loan from the local Regional Rural Bank (RRB) to the extent of Rs. 70,000 and, from his side, invested another Rs. 30,000 and thus, with a sum of Rs. 1 Lakh, he started his mobile repairing unit. He was earning an average of Rs. 8 0000 through the business, as reported in April 2016.

G) West Khasi Hills District, Meghalaya:

These cases are from West Khasi Hills District, Meghalaya. Of the many cases, few names may be mentioned; all belong to tribal communities of Meghalaya. Nongstoin is the headquarters of West Khasi Hills District. D Lynkhoi, Son of K. Kharbani of Nongstoin, Meghalaya, started pig farming with Rs.25,000 as a bank loan and Rs.15,000 as self-investment

and thus earning around Rs15,000 as income per month. Similarly, T. Lyngkhoi, son of H. Marngar, with a bank loan of Rs.25,000 vis-a-vis Rs.20,000 by his own money, earning substantial income (around Rs.16000 per month) through pig farming. Mr. K. Syiem, son of P. Lyngkhoi, after RSETI training, borrowed a bank loan of Rs.70,000 plus Rs.50,000 invested from his sources, started paddy cultivation, and happily earned descend income and kept substantial food grains for home consumption. Similar is the case of .S. Lyngkhoi, son of N. Wahlang; C. Mawlieh, son of P. Nongkharrit; and many others of Nongstoin by borrowing bank loans as well as own money by cultivating paddy were earning handsome income for which they thanked to RSETI, Nongstoin. Further, in Nongstoin, many youths earned a decent income from goat rearing, poultry farming, etc., after RSETI training. According to them, they had ideas, but training helped them to do the activities scientifically. The study was based on 2018-19.

Conclusion:

From the above discussion, through RSETIs, lakhs of youths earned income and supported their families. In many countries, the population was even less than that of trainees under RSETIs. The youths of India can think of undergoing training under RSETI as the proper training will help them settle in the right economic venture. The advantage is that RSETI training allows to get bank loans easily for those who are interested in having them. Also, I suggest to the Government of India that densely populated developed blocks or big subdivisions of the country RSETIs may be set up.

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